

IntegrateMind: A Multidisciplinary Journal

To Cite:

Anorue, D.N. Haemato-Biochemical Indices and Immune Response of Grower Pigs Fed Enzyme Supplemented Dried Cassava Peel –Maize Cob Composite Meal. *IntegrateMind: A Multidisciplinary Journal* 2024; Vol 3, Issue 1, pp. 114-118.

Author Affiliation:

¹Department of Animal Science, University of Abuja, Nigeria.

***Corresponding Author**

¹Department of Animal Science, University of Abuja, Nigeria.

Email: anorued@gmail.com

Peer-Review History

Received: 7th April, 2024

Reviewed & Revised: 08/April / 2024 to 29th May/2024

Accepted: 30th May 2024

Published: May 2024

Peer-Review Model

External peer-review was done through double-blind method.

IntegrateMind: A Multidisciplinary Journal

ISSN: xxxx-xxxx

URL: <https://sites.google.com/view/sherwanjournals/integatemind-journal>

Ethics

Animal studies are presented in this manuscript.

No human studies are presented in this manuscript.

No potentially identifiable human images or data is presented in this study.

License: **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International**

Performance and Carcass Characteristics of Grower Pigs Fed Enzyme Supplemented Dried Cassava Peel –Maize Cob Composite Meal

Daniel Nnadozie Anorue ^{1*}

ABSTRACT

A 90 days' trial was carried out to evaluate the performance and carcass characteristics of grower pigs fed enzyme supplemented dried Cassava peel-maize cob composite meal (CP-MC). A total of 36 crossbred male grower pigs (Large white) of about 16 weeks' old with an initial body weight of 20.31 ± 0.61 kg were randomly allotted into four groups of nine animals per treatment. Each treatment was further divided into three replicates consisting of three pigs in a completely randomized design. Pigs in treatment 1 were fed 0 % CP-MC while CP-MC was used to replace maize at 40 % (T2), 50 % (T3) and 60 % (T4). Diet were adequate in all nutrients, clean water and feed were offered ad libitum. Results on growth performance showed that average daily weight gain were higher in T4 (0.34 kg) and T3 (0.33 kg), intermediate in T2 (0.26 kg) and lower in T1 (0.23 kg) ($P < 0.05$). Similarly, best feed conversion ratio was found among pigs in T4 followed by T3, T2 and T1 ($P < 0.05$). Conversely, average daily feed intake were not influenced by the treatments ($P > 0.05$). Dressing percentage varied from 61.60 – 71.94 % were significantly ($P < 0.05$) different among the treatments. Weights of head, belly, limbs, back fat thickness, kidney liver, lungs and spleen were significantly ($P < 0.05$) different among the treatments. In conclusion, the replacement of maize with CP-MC at 60 % improved the weight of pigs without compromising the performance of animals.

Keywords: Maize; Sswine, Conventional feeds, Carcass.

1. INTRODUCTION

The increasing world population—which is expected to reach eight billion people by November 2022—has led to a rise in the demand for traditional feedstuff used by both humans and pigs (UN, 2022). This is especially true for developing and underdeveloped countries when there is a food shortage brought on by rapid population growth. The competition between the animal feed industry and human consumers drives up the price of these conventional feedstuffs. Research into alternative feed ingredients that aren't staple meals for human consumption is prompted by this. Agro industrial by-products damage the environment and are not being used as possible economic feedstuffs if they are burned or allowed to decay in piles (Ojediran et al., 2020). Pigs and humans have been shown to compete for the same grains and cereals, especially maize (Adesehinwa et al. 2008). The price of maize, a vital source of energy for pig diets, has increased significantly due to growing competition and the effects of climate change, which have reduced production. This shortage has persisted, according to Oladunjoye et al. (2008) and Owen et al. (2009), which has resulted in high production costs, poor profitability, and the inability to satisfy Nigeria's need for animal protein. Peels from cassava and maize cob are one of the many agro-industrial by-products that show potential for usage as a substitute feed substance. It is an essential waste or agricultural by-product that is left over after cassava is processed to make food (Oladunjoye et al., 2010).

SHERWAN
Publishers

Studies involving cassava peel have shown that higher amounts of crude fibre, which functioned as energy diluents and hampered energy utilization, were associated with poorer performance in birds fed cassava peel diets (Ezieshi and Olomu, 2011). Notable researchers Ojediran et al. (2020); Kanengoni et al. (2004) have shown that cassava peel and maize cob can be used to replace maize up to 50 %. The optimal amount of dried cassava peel meal and dried maize cob meal to substitute for maize in pig diets is not well documented. Evaluating the effect of cassava peel –maize cob meal mixture will also help to maximize the potential in the environment, help to formulate a least ratio feed and help to increase the production of animal protein. Therefore, this experiment was designed to evaluate the performance and carcass characteristics of grower pigs fed enzyme supplemented dried Cassava peel –maize cob composite meal.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Site of the experiment

The experiment was carried out at the livestock unit University of Abuja, Gwagwalada Nigeria, located between latitudes 8°57'1" and 8°55'1"N and longitudes 7°05'1"E and 7°06'1"E. It was carried out according to the ethical guidelines and procedures of Animal Science department (ANS/2024A).

2.2. Collection, authentication and processing of Cassava peel and maize cob

Fresh maize cob and cassava peel were collected from a different processing facilities in Gwagwalada, Abuja and transferred to the department of Biological Sciences where it was identified and authenticated with a voucher number AA/2004C and AA/2005D. Thereafter, samples were sundried separately on a flat metallic tray for 15 days until a constant weight was achieved. Dried sample was milled separately using a hammer mill and treated with enzymes before it was mixed in the ratio 1:1 before it was sent to the laboratory for further examination.

2.3. Animals and their management

36 – sixteen weeks' large white grower male pigs with an initial body weight of 20.31 ± 0.60 kg was used for the study. The animals were purchased from a reputable breeder farm in Abuja and transferred to the University of Abuja teaching and research farm, Gwagwalada. On arrival pigs were kept in a pen measuring 2.5 m by 1.0 m by 2 m (length, breadth and width) in an open sided pen thoroughly disinfected two weeks before the commencement of the experiment. Animals were kept in quarantine for a period of two weeks and fed growers mash (basal diet) formulated to satisfy the nutritional needs of pigs in accordance with the NRC's (2002) recommendation. They were also given prophylactic treatment against endo- and ecto parasites before they were stratified based on their body weight into four treatment groups and each treatment was replicated three times with three animals in each replicate in a completely randomized design. Feed and water was offered ad libitum.

2.4. Experimental set-up

Treatment 1 (T1) basal diet without cassava peel-maize cob meal mixture (CP-MC) while in T2, T3 and T4 CP-CM was used to replace maize at 40 %, 50 % and 60 % respectively.

2.5. Parameters examined

Feed was weighed daily for pigs in each replicate and the quantity consumed for the day was obtained by difference between the quantity supplied and the left over. Weekly record of average feed consumption per bird was obtained for each replicate by dividing the total quantity of feed consumed by the number of pigs in each replicate.

The body weight gain was obtained by calculating the difference between the body weight for the preceding week and current week while the feed conversion ratio was determined by dividing the quantity of feed consumed by the body weight gain of the birds in each replicate in grams.

$$\text{Feed conversion ratio (FCR)} = \text{Average daily feed intake (g)} / \text{Average daily weight gain (g)}$$

2.6. Carcass quality assessment

Six pigs from each treatment were chosen at random to prevent bias at the end of the experiment. Before being slaughtered, the chosen pigs underwent a twelve-hour feed fast and were weighed. To guarantee full bleeding, the pigs were shocked and killed by jugular vein piercing, while hanging on a rail, eviscerated and carcass weight measured. The head, boston, shoulder, loin and ham were among the sections of the carcass that were weighed, separated and their respective weights were then divided by the carcass weight and multiplied by 100 to determine the percentage weights of each component. The dressing percentage was computed by dividing the carcass weight with the live weight and multiplying by 100.

2.7. Statistical analysis

Data collected from the study was subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using the computer software package SPSS 21.0; differences among treatment means were compared with Duncan's multiple range test of the same statistical package.

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Growth performance of grower pigs fed CP-CM is presented in Table 1. Final body weight, weight gain and average daily weight gain of pigs fed 50 % replacement (diet 3) were similar ($P<0.05$) to those fed diet 60 % (diet 4) but significantly higher than those fed diet 2 (40 % replacement) and control (T1). Average daily feed intake were similar across the treatments ($P>0.05$). Feed conversion ratio was significantly ($P<0.05$) influenced by the treatments. The substitution of CP-CM in the pigs' diet had a significant impact on performance parameters, and the performance indices increased as the amount of CP-CM in the dietary maize increased. This observed performance can be attributed to a synergy between the pigs' digestive systems and their improved utilization of CP-CM diets treated with enzymes by the grower pigs. This is consistent with findings from Ikurioret al. (1996), who reported that as animals age, they tend to handle fiber more efficiently, and Cheson (2001) who noted that enzymes are a rich source of high-quality protein (amino acids), which compensate for the low quality of crude protein in CP-CM.

The similar impact of dietary treatments on the performance of pigs in T3 and T4 indicates that the mix is appropriate for pigs' diets. The results show that developing pigs fed 50% cassava leaf meal instead of maize performed no differently than the studies by William et al. (2022). The experiment's outcomes, however, are consistent with the findings of Irekhoreet al. (2015), who found that substituting cassava peel for corn had a considerable impact on the performance indices of growing pigs. In addition, Ly et al. (2010); Alagbe (2017), found no discernible changes in the final body weight, average daily gain, dry matter intake, or feed conversion ratio of crossbred pigs fed a diet including dried and ensiled cassava leaf. Pigs fed a CP-CM diet showed an increase in final weight and weight gain; however, this significant difference may be related to the activities of enzymes that promoted weight gain. Beacheminet al. (2003) reported that high producing or growing animals require high levels of available energy to meet the demand for meat production above and beyond maintenance needs; therefore, adding enzymes to energy/high fiber diets would help close the gap between the animal's potential and actual performance by helping to release more digestible energy from fibrous fractions for the animals to use. Dietary supplementation of enzymes treated CP-CM, especially among pigs in T3 and T4, enhanced the nutrient content of feeds (Garcia et al., 2008). Overall results showed that CP-CM based diets were able to support as much growth than the maize-based diet in T1.

Table 1: Growth performance of grower pigs fed CP-CM

Specifications	T1	T2	T3	T4	SEM
Initial weight (kg/pig)	20.91	20.31	20.80	20.54	1.05
Final weight (kg/pig)	41.76 ^c	43.72 ^b	50.15 ^a	50.76 ^a	0.91
Weight gain (kg/pig)	20.85 ^c	23.41 ^b	29.35 ^a	30.22 ^a	1.41
Av. daily wgt gain (kg/day)	0.23 ^c	0.26 ^b	0.33 ^a	0.34 ^a	0.02
Total feed intake (kg/pig)	51.22	51.10	51.63	51.60	1.96
Av. daily feed intake (kg/day)	0.57	0.57	0.57	0.57	0.02
Feed conversion ratio	2.46 ^a	2.18 ^b	1.76 ^c	1.71 ^c	0.06
Mortality (%)	0	0	0	0	-

Note: ^{a,b,c} Means on the same row with different superscripts are significantly different ($P<0.05$); T1: 0 % CP-CM; T2: 40 % CP-CM; T3: 50 % CP-CM; T4: 60 % CP-CM; SEM: standard error of mean

Table 2 presents the carcass characteristics of grower pigs fed dried cassava peel – maize cob mixture as replacement for maize (CP-CM). Carcass weight and dressing percentage values varied from 48.73 - 54.78 kg and 61.61 % - 70.49 % respectively. Dressing percentage was higher in T3 and T4, intermediate in T2 and lowest in T1 ($P<0.05$). Dietary treatment influenced ($P<0.05$) the weights of the head, back, belly, forelimb, hind limb, back fat thickness, liver, lungs, spleen, heart and gastro intestinal tract except for the weight of kidney ($P>0.05$). Weights of the head, back, belly, forelimb, hind limb, liver, lungs, spleen, heart and gastro intestinal tract ranged from 4.88 to 5.85 kg, 6.71 to 8.15 kg, 3.87 to 4.56 kg, 9.96 to 15.36 kg, 10.02 to 15.22 kg, 7.09 to 8.11kg, 0.09 to 1.03 kg, 0.41 to 0.54 kg, 0.10 to 0.15 kg, 0.18 to 0.25 kg and 5.71 to 6.33 kg respectively.

When compared to other treatments, the dressing % of pigs fed the T3 and T4 diet was better, which may have been caused by the meal's ingredients. High-nutrient diets, especially those with readily available energy and protein, exhibit higher tissue accretion and quick protein synthesis (Njoku et al., 2013). Pigs with greater nutritional status consume enough nutrients to support their fast growth and development (Unigwe et al., 2017); Alagbe (2017). Nonetheless, the dressing percentage of pigs fed a diet containing 50% replacement of CP-CM was comparable to that of pigs fed a diet containing 60 % T4 diet. This implies that the pigs have access to enough protein and energy. This also has to do with how enzymes affect CP-CM, helping to release nutrients that have been trapped up in the feed material. Pigs fed CP-CM had higher weights in the primal cut portions, such as the belly and hind limbs, than pigs fed the control diet (T1). This supports the findings of Njoku et al. (2013), who found that the weights of the head, ham, feet, and shoulders were higher in pigs with bigger body weights. Additionally, when the weight at slaughter increased, so did the weights of the ham, shoulder, and loin, according to Lo-Fiego et al. (2005) and Latorreet al. (2008). In a similar vein, pigs fed T3 and T4 had significantly

higher heart weights than the other groups. This may be explained by the phytochemicals in CP-CM, which provide the body's tissues with an ample supply of oxygen (Hong et al., 2016). The liver is linked to nutrition metabolism and secretes bile (Hong et al., 2016).

Table 2: Carcass characteristics of grower pigs fed CP-CM

Specifications (kg)	T1	T2	T3	T4	SEM
Live weight (kg)	41.76 ^c	43.72 ^b	50.15 ^a	50.76 ^a	0.92
Carcass weight (kg)	25.73 ^c	29.38 ^b	36.08 ^a	35.78 ^a	1.65
Dressing percentage (%)	61.61 ^c	67.20 ^b	71.94 ^a	70.49 ^a	1.76
Head (kg)	4.88 ^c	5.21 ^b	5.75 ^a	5.85 ^a	0.18
Back (kg)	6.71 ^c	7.53 ^b	8.00 ^a	8.15 ^a	0.23
Belly (kg)	3.87 ^c	4.10 ^b	4.49 ^a	4.56 ^a	0.02
Fore limb (kg)	9.96 ^c	11.98 ^b	14.70 ^a	15.36 ^a	0.42
Hind limb (kg)	10.02 ^c	13.75 ^b	15.00 ^a	15.22 ^a	0.44
Back fat thickness (mm)	7.09 ^b	7.22 ^b	8.00 ^a	8.11 ^a	0.21
Kidney (kg)	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.02
Liver (kg)	0.09 ^b	0.09 ^b	1.02 ^a	1.03 ^a	0.01
Lungs (kg)	0.41 ^b	0.50 ^a	0.53 ^a	0.54 ^a	0.02
Spleen (kg)	0.10 ^b	0.10 ^b	0.10 ^b	0.15 ^a	0.01
GIT weight (kg)	5.71 ^b	5.88 ^b	6.21 ^a	6.33 ^a	0.02

Note: ^{a, b, c}, Means on the same row with different superscripts are significantly different ($P < 0.05$); T1: 0 % CP-CM; T2: 40 % CP-CM; T3: 50 % CP-CM; T4: 60 % CP-CM; SEM: standard error of mean

4. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, dried cassava peel – maize cob mixture contains essential nutrients and phytochemicals which are needed for the growth of pigs especially when used to replace maize up to 60 %. Phyto-constituent's in CP-CM improved the utilization of nutrients in the gastrointestinal tract of pigs without compromising the health of the animals.

Ethical approval

All international standards have been adopted and compliance.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

Funding

The study has not received any external funding.

Data and materials availability

All data associated with this study are present in the paper.

REFERENCES AND NOTES

1. Adeshinwa, A.O.K., Obi, O.O., Makanjuola, B.A., Oluwole, O.O., & Adesina, M.A. (2011). Growing pigs fed cassava peel based diet supplemented with or without Farmazyme® 3000 proenx: Effect on growth, carcass and blood parameters. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 10, 2791-2796.
2. Alagbe, J.O. (2017). Effect of Miadasan as a dietary supplement on performance, carcass characteristic and blood profile of broiler chicken. *Scholarly Journal of Agricultural Science*, 7(2), 27-33.
3. Alagbe, J.O. (2017). Growth performance and blood parameters of weaner pigs fed diets supplemented with turmeric powder. *Scholarly Journal of Agricultural Science*, 7(2), 57-61.
4. Alagbe, J.O. (2017). Nutrient evaluation of sweet orange (*Citrus sinensis*) fruit peel as a replacement for maize in the diets of weaner grass cutters. *Scholarly Journal of Agricultural Science*, 6(8), 277-282.
5. Alagbe, J.O., Eimoga, A.A., & Alagbe, O.O. (2017). Growth response and carcass characteristics of weaner grass cutters fed diets supplemented with Polyalthialongifolia seed oil as a natural growth promoter. *Greener Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 7(5), 112-119.
6. Alagbe, J.O. (2019). Effects of feeding varying levels of tigernut (*Cyperus esculentus*) seed meal on the performance and blood profile of weaner grass cutters. *Scholarly Journal of Agricultural Science*, 7(1), 15-19.
7. Buchanan, A., Asker, N.E., Aly, M.M., Hala, A.M., Abdel-Wahed, M., & Omar, E.M. (2007). The use of sorghum in broiler and layer diets with reference to enzyme supplementation. *Journal of Agricultural Science, Mansoura University*, 23, 5307-5323.
8. Fiego, L.D.P., Santoro, P., Macchioni, P., & de Leonibus, E. (2005). Influence of genetic type, live weight at slaughter and carcass fatness on fatty acid composition of subcutaneous adipose tissue of raw ham in the heavy pig. *Meat Science*, 69, 107-114.
9. García-Valverde, R., Barea, R., Lara, L., Nieto, R., & Aguilera, J.F. (2008). The effects of feeding level upon protein and fat deposition in Iberian heavy pigs. *Livestock Science*, 114, 263-273.
10. Hong, T.T.T., van An, L., Be, P.T., & Lindberg, J.E. (2016). Effect of fermented rice bran and cassava waste on growth performance and meat quality of crossbred pigs. *World Journal of Agricultural Research*, 4, 132-138.
11. Irekhore, O.T., Adeyemi, O.M., Idowu, O.M.O., Akinola, O.S., & Bello, K.O. (2015). Growth performance, haematological indices and cost benefits of growing pigs fed cassava peel meal diets supplemented with Allzyme® SSF. *International Journal of Applied Agriculture and Apiculture Research*, 11, 51-59.
12. National Research Council (NRC). (2012). *Nutrient requirements of poultry* (9th revised ed.). National Academy of Service.
13. Njoku, C.P., Aina, A.B.J., Sogunle, O.M., Oduguwa, O.O., Adeyemi, O.A., & Ekunseitan, D.A. (2013). Influence of feed quantity offered on linear body measurements, nutrient digestibility, and back fat composition of finishing pigs. *Pacific Journal of Science and Technology*, 14, 387-396.
14. Ojediran, T.K., Olayiwola, S., Adeyeye, M., Ajayi, A.F., & Emiola, I.A. (2020). Effect of palm kernel meal-based diet with or without enzyme supplementation on growth performance, economic benefits and villi morphometry of weaned pigs. *Polish Journal of Natural Sciences*, 35(2), 129-139.
15. Oladunjoye, I.O., Ojebiyi, O.O., & Odunsi, A.A. (2008). Performance, characteristics and egg quality of laying chicken fed lyre treated cassava peel meal. In *Proceedings of the Annual Conference of ASAN* (pp. 355-357). ABU, Zaria.
16. Oladunjoye, I.O., Ojebiyi, O., & Amao, O.A. (2010). Effect of feeding processed cassava (*Manihot esculenta* Crantz) peel meal based diet on the performance characteristics, egg quality and blood profile of laying chicken. *Agricultura Tropica et Subtropica*, 43(2).
17. Owen, O.J., & Amakiri, A.O. (2010). Japanese quail (*Coturnix coturnix Japonica*): Its potentials, opportunities and challenges. In *Proceedings of the 31st Annual Conference of the Nigerian Society for Animal Production* (pp. 333-335). University of Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.
18. Unigwe, C.R., Raji, A.M., Ajayi, J.O., Popoola, A.M., Balogun, F.A., & Adekunle, F.O. (2017). Carcass, organ weights and histo-morphology of internal organs of sows fed fermented and enzyme-supplemented cassava peels meal (CPM) based diets. *Journal of Plant and Animal Sciences*, 2, 26-36.
19. Williams, G.A., Akinola, O.S., Adeleye, T.M., Irekhore, O.T., Oso, A.O., Ayansola, E.I., Oke, I.O., Ogunrombi, J.O., Ogunpitan, K.O., & Bangbose, A.M. (2022). Effect of differently processed cassava peel-leaf blend on growth performance, carcass yield and ileal microflora of growing pigs. *Trends in Agricultural Sciences*, 1(2), 78-86.

Disclaimer/Publisher's Note: The statements, opinions and data contained in all publications are solely those of the individual author(s) and contributor(s) and not of Sherwan Journals and/or the editor(s). Sherwan Journals and/or the editor(s) disclaim responsibility for any injury to people or property resulting from any ideas, methods, instructions or products referred to in the content.